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BEESSNESS PROJECT

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Abstract

Bees are amazing animals harbouring highly complex behaviours (Buchmann, 2023; MaBoudi et al., 2023). Owing to the intensive decline they have been facing, the number of bee-related publications indexed in Scopus increased by over more than 2.5 folds from 2011 to 2020, compared to the previous decade. Nevertheless, information on the distribution and abundance of most bee species is still mostly unknown. Geographic biases creating gaps in the understanding of species distributions and regional patterns of diversity have been identified, indicating research efforts are often focused around cities or field stations associated with universities and other

research institutions (Jamieson et al., 2019). Populations in the Caatinga biome, particularly those of endemic solitary and honey bee species, were included in these knowledge gaps. Caatinga bees provide precious pollinator services to highly exported fruit crops (i.e. manga, passion fruit, barbados cherry) in the São Francisco Valley. Apart from distribution, environmental pressures on bees, such as pollution, floristic composition, plant-pollinator interactions, soil quality and microbial composition were also mostly unknown in the area. In this context, the BEESSNESS project came from the passion and concern of researchers collaborating across the Atlantic Ocean. It was anchored on previous work and expanded in the collaboration among CIIMAR, Cardiff University and Brazilian researchers, who aimed to unravel diversity patterns, pressures, challenges and opportunities to protect bees and support local farmers and beekeepers. Among its specific goals were: to conduct pesticide screenings in various environmental matrices and bee products to identify the most relevant compounds and spot contamination problems in locally produced honey and fruits; to evaluate and compare the diversity of solitary and honeybee communities in these areas; to investigate bees microbiome in relation to pesticide application and molecular responses to the most common pesticides identified; and develop communication actions targeting local stakeholders transferring knowledge about bees, sustainable agriculture practices and their importance to the Atlantic transnational fabric. Between the project launch and the present day, much happened. From lost collaborations to engaging new partners, but most importantly, the highly impacting pandemic by COVID-19. The latter brought the need to reconvert and adapt, rebuild based on the possible research rhythm and exchange. Arriving this day, I am proud to say that despite all constraints and delays, thanks to the commitment of all institutions involved we gathered a wealth of data and results from the work developed. These are presented herein in the following communications. The communications address the part of the results that could be processed up to the moment, more is to come in the near future.

References

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